

Long Term Strength of Glass Reinforced Plastics

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ABSTRACT

Experiments on the long term strength under load of unidirectional glass reinforced epoxy and polyester resins and of glass strands have been conducted for times up to three years.

Two limiting types of behaviour have been characterized quantitatively. In the first, observed with uncoupled glass fibre strands (bundles) the time to failure may be accounted for using a two parameter Weibull distribution of strengths and a crack growth law for the flaws deduced from measurements on bulk glass. The theory will also account for strength retention tests reported in the literature.

In the second mode which is most readily apparent with unidirectional GRP at low pH there is a marked change from the normal fibrous type of fracture at short failure times to a planar fracture at long failure times. If the specimens are regarded as monoliths, then the average time to failure under load can be deduced from short time crack growth experiments on the composite.

1. INTRODUCTION

As part of a comprehensive programme on the long term strength of fibre-reinforced plastics at the National Physical Laboratory, a range of fibres and composites are being subjected to stress-rupture tests. We report here some of the results on glass reinforced plastics which are intended to be used in order to predict a design stress for GRP. Two types of experiment are reported here, the first are stress-rupture tests on thin unidirectional strands of glass with and without resin impregnation. The results can be understood in terms of stress corrosion of a bundle of fibres and the theory can explain the results of other workers. Additional experiments on large specimens in a corrosive environment are explained in terms of stress corrosion of a monolith.

2. UNIDIRECTIONAL STRANDS

In order to test a large number of specimens, it was decided to use resin-impregnated strands (ie bundles of single filaments - 400 in the case of E-glass) which, apart from ease of gripping, have the added advantage, on account of their

small cross-sections, of reaching equilibrium with the environment more rapidly.

Strands were impregnated with either polyester (Crystic 189 LV plus 2% powder catalyst B, Scott Bader & Co Ltd) or epoxy (Ciba-Geigy MY 750 + 10% HY 951) resin and full details are given in reference (1). The chemical composition of the E-glass and Cemfil are given in Table 3. Results of the stress rupture tests in ambient laboratory conditions, are shown in Fig 1 - the fall-off in strength of the impregnated strands is quite rapid and is larger than the decrease in strength predicted from matrix effects alone (2).

Fig 1 Stress rupture of polyester impregnated strands tested under ambient conditions 0 and after presoaking in distilled water for 10^5 minutes

Figure 2 shows the degradation in strength as a function of time of immersion in distilled water for unimpregnated E-glass strands. A marked decrease in strength is found.

Fig 2 Stress rupture of E-glass strands in distilled water.

The surprising results are shown in Figs 3 and 4. Here there is a rapid reduction of strength under wet conditions to around one sixth of the original strength irrespective of whether the impregnating resin is polyester or epoxy.

Fig 3 Stress rupture of E-glass strands impregnated with polyester resin in distilled water

Fig 4 Stress rupture of E-glass strands impregnated with epoxy resin in distilled water

After times of more than 1000 minutes the strengths are the same in these impregnated strands as in the unimpregnated E-glass strands. In contrast to this behaviour when unstressed impregnated strands were soaked for 10^5 minutes (ie for a time which, had they been under stress, would have resulted in a strength reduction of 80%) and then dried under ambient conditions, their stress rupture performance was only very slightly reduced (see Fig 1).

Under slow cycle (0.1 Hz) fatigue conditions, the total time to failure under wet conditions for a given load is similar to that under static load although the fatigue specimens were only actually under load for half the time shown. Bearing in mind that many of the specimen lives exceed 10^6 cycles at a strain which caused failure in some of the static specimens in the same time, it is quite clear that any additional reduction in strength as a result of fatigue in unidirectional GRP is quite small under these conditions, (1).

The results shown in Figs 3 and 4 indicate that the resin has very little effect after times of 1000 minutes. Table 1 shows values for the diffusion coefficient of water in various resins taken from ref 3 which indicate that after time of 1000 minutes a thickness of specimen of some $100 \mu\text{m}$ will be saturated with water. This is comparable with the thickness of our specimens.

Table 1

Diffusion of water in various resins Values of the Diffusion coefficient $D_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and of the distance $\chi = \sqrt{Dt}$ for $t = 1000 \text{ min}$				
	23°C		60°C	
	$D(\text{cm}^2/\text{sec})$	$\sqrt{Dt}(\text{cm})$	$D(\text{cm}^2/\text{sec})$	$\sqrt{Dt}(\text{cm})$
u.p. Standard Resin	2.75×10^{-9}	1.28×10^{-2}		
Mat laminate (30% glass)	3.75×10^{-9}	1.53×10^{-2}		
u.p. Bisphenol A	4×10^{-8}	4.9×10^{-2}	4×10^{-7}	1.55×10^{-2}
E.P. Bisphenol A	3×10^{-9}	1.34×10^{-2}	8×10^{-9}	2.2×10^{-2}
E.P. Bisphenol A glass fabric 50-60%	2.5×10^{-9}	1.22×10^{-2}	7×10^{-9}	2.0×10^{-2}
Epoxy - Ciba Geigy information	2.3×10^{-9}	1.17×10^{-2}		

Cemfil is an alkali-resistant glass containing zirconia developed by Pilkington Brothers as a reinforcement for cement. Since the failure of the E-glass strands seemed to be dominated by stress corrosion, independently of the resin used, it was logical to test more chemically resistant glass. We found its performance relative to E-glass is much improved, and there was little decrease in strength of unimpregnated strands even after a year, the decrease in strength being from 6 GPa to 4.5 GPa in times of much greater than a year.

The plots of log load v log time shown in Figs 1, 2, 3 and 4 indicate decrease in strength with time at long times of the form $\frac{F}{F_0} \propto t^{-1/n}$ where n is about 15 for unimpregnated strands, 8 for those impregnated with polyester and about 4 for those impregnated with epoxy. It was identification of the value of n for unimpregnated strands with the known values of the stress exponent for glass in an equation of the type of (2) (see below) that led us to develop a theory of bundle failure based upon stress corrosion which accounts well for the results in Fig 2 and for the results in Figs 3 and 4 at long times (4).

The theory can also account for the experimentally determined fraction of fibres breaking as a function of time under load. This is shown in Fig 5. Although the times to failure depend principally upon the stress exponent n, the

experimentally determined fraction of fibres broken as a function of time depends much more upon the exponent m in the Weibull distribution.

Fig 5 Experimentally determined fraction of fibres broken as a function of time for E-glass bundles in water, compared with the theoretical prediction from reference 4. x and o are point corresponding to two different loads.

An interesting feature of these results has been explored further by McCartney (5). He has found that, even at long lives, there is very little decrease of the measured strength of a bundle with time until just before final fracture of the whole bundle. This means that the concept of measuring strength retention as an indication of remaining life is very likely to be unreliable, as Chiao and others (6) have found experimentally. In fact the theory of bundle failure is able to account for Chiao's results on impregnated strands of glass fibre.

Consider the experimental results of Chiao et al shown in Fig 4 of ref 5. We identify the failure line representing 100% failure with our calculated failure load versus time curve. For their spool I it follows from their Table 3 that the short time strength of a strand is approximately 590 ksi (average of batch and winding process data). In their Fig 4 the 100% of failure line decreases from 550 ksi to 360 ksi in five decades of time ($0.1h \leq t_f \leq 10^4h$). Thus the applied load (F) divided by the maximum load bearing capacity ie (F/F_m) decreases from approximately 0.95 to 0.6 during this interval of time. In order to relate this strand behaviour to that predicted by the Kelly and McCartney (4) loose bundle model it is necessary to extend the data presented in Fig 3 of Kelly and McCartney. Our calculations show that when $n = 25$ the loose bundle model predicts that (F/F_m) decreases from 0.95 to 0.6 in five decades of time and thus the experimental behaviour for strands observed by Chiao et al can be modelled on the assumption that $n = 25$ in their case. More significantly it is possible to use the loose bundle model to estimate the strength retention of a loose bundle during its progressive failure caused by stress corrosion mechanisms, as described by McCartney (6).

So as to avoid guessing parameters such as K_{1C} , the critical stress intensity factor, σ_0 (which is related to the mean strength of the fibres) and α see equat(2) for the S glass fibres, which would be necessary to account for the absolute times to failure, we confine ourselves to considering strength retention at given fractions of the total failure time (t_f). Let t_0 be the elapsed time from loading until the residual strength of a loose bundle in an aggressive environment reduces to 95% of its initial strength. Table 2 indicates the dependence of t_0/t_f on the parameter (F/F_m) when $n = 25$ and $m = 8$.

It is seen that more than 95% of the initial strength of the loose bundle is retained for more than 89% of the life for all values of applied loads such that (F/F_m) \leq 0.8. This result suggests that the unexpectedly high retention of strength of impregnated strands reported by Chiao et al (7) and shown in their Fig 3 can be attributed to the behaviour of fibre bundles in aggressive

environments, neglecting the mechanical effect of the matrix.

Table 2

F/F_m	t_o/t_f (%)
1	0
0.8	89
0.6	89.1
0.4	89.5

3. TENSILE SPECIMENS OF GRP

Much thicker carefully made unidirectional specimens of minimum thickness 1mm, width 15 mm, and gauge length 125mm, have been fabricated by winding single strands, that is bundles of glass, on to square sheets of perspex by means of a coil winder. E-glass strands contain more fibres than the Cemfil (total cross sectional areas of glass $12.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2$ and $2.83 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2$ respectively) and the pitch of the coil winder was adjusted to give the same glass content per layer. Unidirectional specimens contained 14 layers. The chemical composition of the glasses are shown in Table 3.

Table 3

Chemical composition of E-glass and Cemfil	
	SiO ₂ K ₂ O Na ₂ O B ₂ O ₃ Al ₂ O ₃ MgO CaO ZrO ₂ Li ₂ O
E-glass	52.4 0.8 10.4 14.4 5.2 16.6 - -
Cemfil	71 11 - 1 - - 16 1

All specimens were made with Scott Bader Crystic 189 LV (orthophthalic) polyester resin with 2% catalyst M and 0.05% accelerator E. The details are given in (8). To compare the performance of E-glass and Cemfil composites in H₂SO₄ a static load was applied to specimens contained in a glass tube and time to failure recorded. The effect of square wave loading on the E-glass composite in acid conditions was investigated using a 0.1 Hz waveform in tension between maximum and 0.1 maximum load. A number of E-glass specimens were immersed in acid for a period 1.8×10^6 s prior to testing. Most of the tests were conducted on an Instron 1272 servo hydraulic machine but a mechanical lever-arm incorporating a variable cam, designed and built at NPL, was also used for the long term fatigue tests. Double cantilever beam specimens were prepared from cross ply material and were used to measure slow crack growth normal to the fibres in a 1 N sulphuric acid environment. The crack tip was observed with a travelling microscope and the load applied either through the Instron crosshead or by means of a cantilever and dead weight system for longer times. Time intervals were chosen so that changes of K_1 resulting from load change or crack length were small and mean values over the time interval were used.

3a. Long term strength

Times to failure of unidirectional E-glass GRP as a function of tensile stress under both static and 0.1 Hz square wave fatigue loading (no reverse load) are shown in Fig 6. The time plotted for the fatigue specimens is the time actually under maximum load, ie one half the elapsed time. Also shown are the failure times of specimens which had been conditioned in acid (for 1.8×10^6 s) before loading. Failure surfaces, illustrated in Fig 7, were analogous to those observed in the crack growth experiments - see below. Long term failure showed a

Fig 6 Static and fatigue loading of unidirectional GRP in 1N H₂SO₄

comparatively flat fracture surface (b) whereas short term failures (c) tended towards the brush-like appearance normally associated with failure of GRP in air (a). In contrast, Cemfil GRP specimens were hardly affected at all by acid and invariably failed in a brush-like manner. A few results were obtained for unidirectional E-glass GRP in air. The rate of reduction of strength with time at about five per cent per decade was found to be actually greater than that of Cemfil GRP in acid and is consistent with our previous work (1) on polyester impregnated E-glass strands in air. Clearly stress corrosion is present, even in ambient conditions.

Fig 7 a) Short term failure in air; b) Long term failure in acid (10⁵s)
c) Short term failure in acid (450s)

3b. Crack growth measurements

The results are shown in Fig 8. The stress intensity K_1 was calculated from the equation given by Wiederhorn and Bolz (9)

$$K_1 = \left\{ \frac{Pa}{(wb)^{1/2} h^{3/2}} \right\} \left\{ 3.47 + 2.32 \frac{h}{a} \right\} \quad (1)$$

where P is the load, a the crack length, h the height of each cantilever of width w and b the web thickness. Equation (1) was originally derived for an isotropic material, but it can be shown that it is a good approximation for the situation considered here, and is exact for small h/a where only bending moments need to be considered.

Fig 8 Variation of crack velocity normal to the fibres with stress intensity for an unidirectional E-glass polyester composite in 1N sulphuric acid. Crosses denote fatigue loading.

A linear least squares fit to the points in Fig 8 above log V = -7.9 gives a slope of 3.1. To simplify the following discussion we approximate this to 3, well within experimental scatter, indicated by the broken line in Fig 8. The intercept which we designate as log α then becomes -10.02 and so we have

$$V = \frac{da}{dt} = \alpha K_1^n = 9.55 \times 10^{-11} K_1^3 \quad (2)$$

At low K_1 where crack velocities are less than $10^{-8} \text{ m sec}^{-1}$ (ie about 1 mm per day) the points begin to depart significantly from this line and there is some evidence of a stress corrosion limit. At low crack velocities the fracture surface is observed to be essentially planar but the amount of fibre pull-out increases with increase in crack velocity until a point is reached at about $10^{-6} \text{ m sec}^{-1}$ where there is no well defined crack front but solely a damage zone around the tip of the initial crack. In two experiments where a sine wave alternating load (between zero and that corresponding to K_1) was applied, the crack velocities were almost a factor of ten lower. Crack growth measurements were not possible in any of our experiments with Cemfil-GRP specimens because a zone of damage formed at the tip of the initial crack and this merely increased in dimension as the load increased.

4. DISCUSSION

In the case of the thick specimens immersed in acid described in sections 3a and 3b above, we have found that the results can be understood from the crack growth experiments if each thick specimen is regarded as a monolith and hence no account is taken of the discrete nature of the reinforcement.

We follow Wiederhorn (9) and Evans (10) for monolithic specimens. Assume

that the specimen either already contains flaws or cracks of length a_i or that cracks of this length may be easily formed at low stress by some mechanism, eg by multiple cracking. We further assume that subsequent growth obeys equation (2), that is $v = da/dt = K_1^n$ where $K_1 = \sigma_a Y a^{n/2}$. σ_a is the applied stress, a the crack length at time t and Y a geometrical factor equal to $\pi^{1/2}$ for a centre crack. K_1 increases as a result of increasing crack length to a value K_{1c} at which catastrophic failure occurs. The time to failure t_c is given by

$$t_c = \int_{a_i}^{a_{1c}} \frac{da}{v} = \int_{K_{1i}}^{K_{1c}} \frac{2}{\sigma_a^2 Y^2} \frac{K_1}{v} dK_1 = \frac{2}{\sigma_a^2 Y^2 \alpha (n-2)} \left[\frac{K_{1i}^{2-n}}{2-n} - \frac{K_{1c}^{2-n}}{2-n} \right] \quad (3)$$

If the initial flaw size a_i is sufficiently small, $K_{1i} \ll K_{1c}$ and since $n > 2$ we neglect K_{1c} and substitute $K_{1i} = \sigma_a Y a_i^{n/2}$ to obtain,

$$t_c = \frac{2K_{1i}^{2-n}}{(n-2)\alpha \sigma_a^2 Y^2} = \frac{2a_i^{(1-n/2)}}{(n-2)\alpha \sigma_a^n Y^n} \quad (4)$$

Hence the time to failure is inversely proportion to σ_a^n and a plot of log stress versus log time to failure should be linear with a slope $-1/n$ at long times. For $n = 3$, and putting $K_{1c} = \sigma_{\max} Y a_i^{n/2}$ where σ_{\max} is the measured short term ultimate tensile strength, equation (3) reduces to

$$t_c = \frac{2}{\alpha \sigma_a^2 Y^2} \left\{ \frac{1}{K_{1i}} - \frac{1}{K_{1c}} \right\} = \frac{2}{\alpha \sigma_a^3 Y^3 a_i^{3/2}} \left\{ 1 - \frac{\sigma_a}{\sigma_{\max}} \right\} \quad (5)$$

The initial crack length a_i is unknown and so to test this equation we fit it at one point, then establish whether the remaining points fit the predicted curve, and finally whether the resulting value of a_i is plausible. The line in Fig 6 was obtained by fitting at $\sigma_a = 460 \text{ MN m}^{-2}$, $t = 2000$ secs and $\sigma_{\max} = 1000 \text{ MN m}^{-2}$. The fit is quite good over five decades of time but there is some deviation at the longest times corresponding to an initial strain of about 0.3%; there are analogous deviations in the crack growth experiment (Fig 8). This suggests the possible existence of a stress corrosion limit and is consistent with the observation of Collins (11) that stress corrosion cracking did not occur at strains less than 0.3%. The computed value of the initial flaw size a_i is 0.14 mm, which is of the same order as the strand thickness. The strands are in fact elliptical with axes of 0.1 mm and 1 mm.

It is thus tempting to speculate that a crack starts at an exposed fibre under the combined influence of environment and stress, passes easily through a single strand to give an initial crack of the order of the strand size and then propagates more slowly through the composite, being retarded at the resin-rich regions between the strands.

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